

Generative AI engineering with LLMs Specialization
By IBM on Coursera
study notes

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1. Generative AI and LLMs: Architecture and data preparation.

- The training approaches of different training architectures are as in the table:

Model	Training Approach
RNN	Loop-Based Design
Transformers	Self-attention mechanism
GANs	Competitive approach
VAEs	Characteristics-based
Diffusion model	Based on statistical properties

- Generative AI implements Reinforcement learning to train and optimize the models.
- Gen AI shows improved functions:
 - Context awareness.
 - Coherent interactions.
 - Sentiment analysis.
- Gen AI for NLP evolution:
 - rule based system
 - statistical machine learning approach
 - deep learning architectures
 - transformer
- Some of the problems caused by AI hallucinations:
 - Generation of inaccurate information.
 - Creation of biased views.
 - Wrong input provided to sensitive applications.
- Some methods for mitigating hallucinations:
 - Eliminating any bias in training data.
 - Avoiding manipulation of the inputs that are fed into the model.
 - ongoing evaluation and improvement of the model.
 - Fine-tuning a pre-trained LLM on domain-specific data.
- Some of the libraries for machine learning:
 - PyTorch.
 - TensorFlow.
 - HuggingFace: provides three libraries:
 - Transformers
 - Datasets:
 - Tokenizers: for handling pre-tokenization requirements needed for models like BERT and GPT.
 - LangChain: a framework streamlines AI application development, using (LLMs).
 - Pydantic: a library that help streamline data handling, used to parse and validate data and uses Python-type annotation.
- Tokenization: breaking the sentence into smaller pieces. And it has three methods:
 - Word-based. Preserves meaning
 - Character based. Smaller vocabulary
 - Subword based. Such as:
 - WordPiece.
 - Unigram.
 - SentencePiece.
- Processes get applied on text data are:
 - Tokenizing the data.

- Numericalizing it.
- Resizing.
- Tensor conversion.

2. Gen AI Foundational Models for NLP & Language Understanding.

- The Bag-of-Words is the sum of the one-hot vectors of the whole document or sentence. Where one-hot vector can be assigned to each word, character, or other group of characters.
- The embedding bag is a similar concept to a bag-of-words but for embedding vectors instead of one-hot vectors.
- When calculating the loss for a neural network, the KL Divergence function is for calculating the difference between the natural logarithm of the true probability distribution and the natural logarithm of the conditional probability distribution of the true label given the input and the weights, multiplied by the ground truth probability distribution.
- Monte Carlo Sampling is applying a function to a group of samples, divided by the number of them. And it can be applied to approximate the true cross-entropy loss.
- N-Gram models context sizes for example, in bi-gram models the model decides the next word based only on the meaning of the previous word, while in tri-gram models choosing the word depends on two of the previous words. And so on for N words.
- Using the N-Gram model can choose and design the neural network architecture. Where the input layer size get set as = vocabulary size (embedding size) x context size.
- Word2Vec is about changing the word alphabetical representation into numerical representation, by setting a window width, and word index.
- Continuous bag of words (CBOW): is used when the model receives two words and work on predicting a third one in between.
- Skip-gram is the opposite of the (CBOW), where the model works on predicting the surrounding words by knowing the target words.
- Perplexity is a metric to measure the efficiency of the LLMs and the GenAI models and it is calculated as the exponential of the cross entropy loss from the model. Lower perplexity means better performance. It is to measure how well the model learned the training set.
- Other evaluation metrics:
 - NLTK library:
 - BLEU
 - METEOR
 - PyTorch library:
 - Perplexity
 - Other libraries:
 - BLEU
 - ROUGE

3. Generative AI Language Modeling with Transformers

- Positional encoding useful to keep the meaning of the language. And it is a trainable parameter in some models
- The encoding is a sine or cosine function value get assigned to each token.
- Segment embedding is related to positional encoding and it keeps the segment of the token.
- The attention mechanism is similar in concept to dictionaries in python, but instead of having a value for each key, there is a list of number (embedding) for the key and another for the value.
- The query is the word that are looking for a change such as in a translation system the french word that is looking to be translated to english, and the keys and values are the dictionary consisting of keys in french and values in english.
- The self-attention mechanism works on predicting the next word in the sentence.

- The query, key and value in the self-attention mechanism is the input features multiplied by the corresponding weights matrix added to it the bias matrix.
- Types of attention:
 - Scaled dot-product attention.
 - Multi-head attention.
- Cross attention is same as the self-attention in the Scaled dot-product attention network but when the data for the key and value comes from two different sources.
- When building a transformer the embedding dimension must be divisible by the number of heads.
- When building a transformer, the language data is processed in the following steps:
 - Create iterators and allocate training set
 - Generate tokens and construct a vocabulary
 - Design a custom collate function
 - Apply padding
 - Create a data loader
 - Add positional encoding
 - Apply encoder layers
- Decoder based models:
 - GPT:
 - LLaMA
 - Granite
- Autoregressive models are the ones work with time-sequential data and forecasts the future.
- contextual embeddings are different from static embeddings by counting for the surroundings of the word instead of assigning an embedding regardless of the context.
- Self-Attention masking is applied to ensure the decoder only pays attention to the previous tokens, and a decoder can be transferred into an encoder by applying masking, besides that it preserves the autoregressive properties and it is only useful when making predictions and inference.
- Causal attention masking is applied to ensure the decoder is attending for the previous tokens or the token itself, without considering the future tokens.
- Collate function takes a block of text and produces another block of text more suitable for the GPT model training with a standard length to be used as a sample.
- Building GPT is done using the following function:
 - Sample
 - Collate
 - mask and pad
 - position encode
 - Embed
 - decoder
 - feed forward
- **Videos for implementing the embeddings, masking and encoder, decoder architectures in PyTorch are shared in videos.**
- GPT and BERT are self-supervised learning models. With supervised fine-tuning.
- Bidirectional encoder representations for transformers (BERT) is an encoder only model, it is not autoregressive so they do not generate text but do other tasks. Such as predicting a word in the center of a sentence using a Bidirectional approach (MLM). Or Next Sentence prediction (NSP).
- One of the training objectives of the BERT is MLM which uses Unsupervised learning, and the second is NSP.
- Three types of embeddings are used:
 - Positional embeddings
 - Token embeddings
 - Segment embeddings
- Building a simple encoder transformer is done using the following steps:
 - Create embeddings
 - Positional encoding

- Encoder layer
- classifier
- The BERT architecture is built of:
 - Initialization
 - embedding layer
 - Transformer encoder
 - Next sentence prediction
 - Masked language modeling
 - forward pass
- For inference there is a separate approach for each of the objectives.

4. Generative AI Engineering and Fine-Tuning Transformers

- Possible pitfalls for fine-tuning:
 - Overfitting
 - Underfitting
 - Catastrophic forgetting
 - Data leakage
- Types of fine-tuning:
 - Self-supervised fine-tuning.
 - Supervised fine-tuning.
 - Full fine-tuning
 - Parameter efficient fine-tuning (PEFT).
 - Reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF).
- Direct preference optimization (DPO) is an optimization method based directly on human preferences.
- The Hugging Face SFT model trainer makes the model training more simple and less error prone.
- Parameter Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT): is a supervised fine-tuning method, that reduces the number of parameters needs to be updated and the computation resources needed, it has many methods:
 - Selective fine-tuning: Which updates a group of the model layers instead of the full model.
 - Additive fine-tuning: involves adding new layers to the model trained on the new specific task. By adding adapters. Or Soft prompts are learnable tensors concatenated with the embeddings, Some of its methods are:
 - Prompt tuning.
 - Prefix tuning.
 - P-Tuning.
 - Multitask prompt tuning.
 - Reparametrization fine-tuning: such as:
 - Low-rank adaptation (LoRA) where low ranking means reducing the number of parameters and LoRA works by adding new layers to capture the most effective parameters and neurons of the model to keep and ignore the others, by adding the (Δw) term to the weights of the key, value and query. In other words it is about applying a bottleneck.
 - Quantized Low-rank Adaptation (QLoRA): which compose quantization with low rank adaptation
 - Weight-Decomposed low-Rank Adaptation (DoRA): adjust the rank of the low-rank space.
- Quantization means cutting down the count of the numbers used for representing the tokens or reduce the precision of the floating number, and QLoRA uses the following types of quantization:
 - 4-bit NF4
 - Double quantization
- QLoRA reduces the memory foot print up to 75%.
- Some of the model quantization techniques are:
 - Uniform quantization
 - Non-uniform quantization
 - Weight clustering
 - Pruning

5. Generative AI Advance Fine-Tuning for LLMs

- Instruction tuning:
 - Named Supervised Fine Tuning (SFT).
 - applicable after pre-training and before performing DPO or RLHF.
 - It is applicable on transformer decoder based models.
- Instruction tuning datasets consists of:
 - Instructions: to direct the model what to do.
 - Input: a prompt such as a question.
 - Output: response such as an answer.
- The loss cross entropy is calculated for instruction tuning between the model output logits and the next token in the sequence.
- Some times masked instruction tuning improve the results.
- When training the model using SFT it needs defining a collator, which helps pad sequences, create attention masks, handle special tokens and aggregate sequences.
- Reward modeling: is the bases of RLHF and it works by assigning scores to the answers at training time and responding according to the score at inference. And the scores get learned from the dataset. Where an example dataset for the reward modeling is a dataset includes a query (question), a positive response (scientific response), and a negative response (parody response).
- It uses the Bradley-Terry loss to ensure the best response receives the higher score.
- Implementing the instruction tuning and the reward modeling is implemented using hugging face only.
- maximum sequence length supported by the model is crucial, as pretrained transformers have a fixed maximum token length, for example, GPT-2 has 1024 tokens.
- Sampling in LLMs depends on the softmax function distribution.
- Generation parameters in the LLMs such as:
 - Temperature
 - Top K sampling
 - Beam search
 - Top P sampling
 - Max and min tokens
 - Repetition penalty
- In Reinforcement Learning (RL) a policy is a strategy or mapping for the agent to decide its action based on the current environment.
- RLHF works by using a reward model that get the input and output pair of the LLM and generate reward value based on the quality of the response

- The policy gradient is what to be maximized and Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) method is the way to achieve this. And there are many algorithms need to be used to build a system that can deliver it. As shown in the figure.

- Each of the colored boxes in the figure is a math function that get used fully or partially in building the policy gradient or the PPO.
 - The clipped surrogate objective: stabilize the training by ensuring updates to the policy.
 - KL penalty coefficient: regulate the divergence between old and new policies
 - Advantage function: estimate the reward
 - Log derivative trick: provides insight into optimizing the problem
- the policy gradient method is similar to the reward in RLHF which needs to be maximized.
- The loss function for training PPO is KL divergence.
- Direct preference optimization (DPO) is a human preference method designed to improve the model more efficiently than PPO
- DPO is an improved version of RLHF delivering improved results to PPO by enabling training the reward model on simple classification loss.
- The DPO consists of three models
 - reward function which uses an encoder model
 - Target decoder
 - reference model
- DPO delivers state-of-the-art on reinforcement learning while it is more computationally affordable.
- The partition function is the function for the values of $y = 0$ and $y = 1$, from a sigmoid function distribution.
- Objective function according to the course terminology is the loss function in model training.
- DPO does not use numerical representations for the reward model, but it uses Bradley-Terry probability model to compare the accepted with the not accepted sentences.
- To fine-tune a language model with DPO and Hugging Face:
 - Step 1: Data preprocessing
 - Reformat
 - Define and apply the process function
 - Create the training and evaluation sets
 - Step 2: Create and configure the model and tokenizer

- Step 3: Define training arguments and DPO trainer
 - Step 4: Plot the model's training loss
 - Step 5: Load the model
 - Step 6: Inferencing
- DPO leverages a closed-form optimal policy as a function of the reward to reformulate the problem
 - Reward policy:

$$\pi_r(Y|X) = \frac{\pi_{ref}(Y|X) \exp\left(\frac{1}{\beta} r(X, Y)\right)}{Z(X)}$$

- Subtracting the reward model for two samples eliminates the need for the partition function

$$r(X, Y_w) - r(X, Y_l) = \beta \ln\left(\frac{\pi_r(Y_w|X)}{\pi_{ref}(Y_w|X)}\right) - \beta \ln\left(\frac{\pi_r(Y_l|X)}{\pi_{ref}(Y_l|X)}\right)$$

- Loss function:

$$-\sigma\left(\beta \ln\left(\frac{\pi_r(Y_w|X)}{\pi_{ref}(Y_w|X)}\right) - \beta \ln\left(\frac{\pi_r(Y_l|X)}{\pi_{ref}(Y_l|X)}\right)\right)$$

6. Fundamentals of AI Agents Using RAG and LangChain

- Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) works in the following steps:
 - Embedding the inputs as vectors, the prompt and the knowledge based documents get broken down into chunks and embedded as vectors then inserted into a vector database with Dense Passage Retrieval (DPR).
 - Retrieval where the system retrieve the information similar to the prompt from the database and select three to five similar vectors.
 - Create an augmented query encoded with a transformer encoder such as BART and input it to the Chatbot (Transformer).

- RAG can help keep the Chatbot up-to-date and save maintenance time and effort.
- Facebook AI Similarity Search (FAISS) is used to calculate the distance between the embeddings of the prompt and the data base embeddings.
- LangChain is an open-source framework helps develop application using LLM.
- The LangChain framework consists of many libraries:
 - Chains
 - Agents
 - Retrieval strategies
 - LangChain Core
 - LangChain community
- LangChain use cases:
 - build chatbots and AI agents
 - Simplify API integration
 - analyze code and documents
 - Generates question and answers
 - Summaries text
 - information retrieval
 - content management
- In-context learning is a prompt engineering method, in which provide examples for the task as part of the prompt. The model does not need training but learn from the prompts at inference time.
- Prompt types:
 - Zero-shot learning
 - One-shot learning
 - Few-shot learning
 - Chain-of-thought
 - Self-consistency
- LangChain components:
 - Documents: it process documents to be used in RAG applications, where it load from websites or URLs, split, embed, store, retrieval
 - Chains: chains are a sequence of calls, the earlier's answer is used as input in the later one.
Memory in LLMs is used for reading and writing historical data, which is used when working with chains
 - Agents: are dynamic systems where a language model determines and sequences actions such as pre-defined chains. The model generates text outputs to guide actions, but does not execute them directly. However, agents integrate with tools such as search engines, databases, and websites to fulfill user requests.
 - Language Model from IBM, OpenAI, Google, Meta
 - Chat Model is used for chatting and having conversations.
 - Chat Message which has many types:
 - Human message
 - AI message
 - System message
 - Function message

- Tool message
- Prompt Templates types of prompt templates:
 - StringPrompt template.
 - ChatPrompt templates
 - MessagePrompt template.
 - Message Place holder
 - FewShotPrompts template
- Output Parsers: which transforms the output of the LLM to a more suitable format to generate structured data. Includes libraries such as: JSON, CSV, Panda, XML.

* Source: https://python.langchain.com/v0.1/docs/modules/data_connection/

7. Project: Generative AI Applications with RAG and LangChain

- BeautifulSoup is a library for loading and parsing websites and web links. And create documents understandable by LangChain, to be used as RAG documents.
- Text splitters in LangChain works in a few steps:
 - They split the documents into small chunks.
 - Combining the small chunks into larger ones with specific size.
 - Combining the large chunks with overlap to have common context.
- Key parameters in the splitter:
 - Separator.
 - Chunk size.
 - Chunk overlap
 - Length function
- Types of splitters:
 - Character splitters
 - Recursive split by character.
 - Split code
 - Markdown header text splitter.
- Vector databases are optimized for storing and retrieving vectors from the database, unlike the traditional databases which struggle in saving and searching for vectors. For example a database supported by LangChain is ChromaDB and FAISS.
- Types of retrievers:

- LangChain retriever is more general than a vector database, it takes a query as input and returns a document or a set of documents as output. In their simplest types is the vector store-based retriever.
- The retriever uses algorithms to retrieve the documents from the vector database such as:
 - Similarity search.
 - Maximum marginal relevance (MMR) which is a technique used to balance the relevance and diversity of retrieved results.
- Another type of retrievers is the Multi-Query retriever, which uses an LLM to create richer query to retrieve documents.
- Self-query retriever, is used when there is Meta-data to be retrieved in addition to the text documents.
- Parent document retriever which retrieve a small chunk at first then use the ID to find its parent document.

The End

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